

ARRIVAL AND PRICES OF MAJOR COMMODITY IN VITTHAL KRUSHI UTPANNA BAZAR PVT. LTD. IN WASHIM DISTRICT

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MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised:16.09.2024; MS Accepted:17.09.2024)

MS 3289

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRIBUSINESS MANAGEMENT.)

Abstract

The Research Project titled "Arrival and Prices of Major Commodity in Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim District" The present investigation was undertaken to study the arrivals and prices of major commodities in vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. ltd. in washim with the objectives viz., to study the profile of vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. ltd. in washim , to study the compound growth rate in arrivals and prices of major commodities, to study the variability in arrival and prices of major commodities, to study the correlation between arrival and prices of major commodities, to workout the seasonal indices of arrival and prices of major commodities and to identify the constraints and advantages of selected farmers in vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. ltd, washim was selected purposively for the study. The market information relating to market arrival and prices over a period of time helps the farmers to take decision about the future production pattern and sale of agricultural commodities in the market during specific period. The Primary and secondary data were collected from vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. ltd in washim for the period of 10 years since 2014-2023. The data were analysed with simple statistical tools for fulfilling set objectives. compound growth rate in arrival and prices, coefficient of variability, correlation coefficient, seasonal indices were estimated by using appropriate statistical technique and a sample of 30 farmers was drawn from the selected vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. Ltd. in washim . Garret's ranking technique was used to analyze the advantages and constraints faced by farmers at meaningful conclusions.

Keywords: CGR, Arrivals, Prices, Constraints, Advantages, Garret's ranking

Introduction and Objectives

Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Private Limited is a private incorporated on 2 July 2012. It is classified as Non- government company and is registered at Registrar of Companies, Mumbai. The 4 directors of Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Private Limited are Kamal kishore Bhawarilal Baheti ,Pravin Jamanlal Baheti , Purshottam Bhawarilal Baheti and Ram Bhawarilal Baheti. Current status of vitthal krushi utpanna bazar private limited is – Active .The annual turnover of Vitthal Krishi Utpanna Bazar private Limited in terms of money is 250-300cr. Agricultural Produce Market Committees (APMC) is the marketing board established by the state governments in order to by the state governments in order to eliminate the exploitation incidences of the farmers by the intermediaries , where they are forced to sell their produce at extremely low prices.

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To Study the Profile of Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim District.
2. To Estimate the trends in arrival and prices of major commodities.
3. To Workout the Seasonal Indices of arrival and prices of major commodities.
4. To Identify the Constraints and Advantages of selected farmer in Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Pvt . Ltd . in Washim ,District.

3. Materials and Methods

The present study has based on the data of arrivals and prices of major commodity in vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. ltd. in washim district. The study was conducted in Washim district of the eastern Vidarbha region in Maharashtra. This district is purposely selected for the study, which contributes major private APMC in Washim. The production of cereals, oilseeds and commercial crop. Washim is one of the important district in Maharashtra contributes proportional share in the area under oilseeds, pulses, cereals and turmeric. The primary and secondary data were collected from vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. ltd in washim for the period of 10 years since 2014-2023. the secondary data pertaining to arrival and prices for soyabean, pigeon pea, gram and turmeric. the sample of 30 farmers was drawn from the selected vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. ltd. in washim. garret's ranking technique was used to analyze the advantages and constraints faced by farmers at meaningful conclusions.

Tools of analysis

3.1 Trends in Arrival and Prices

The time series data pertaining to monthly arrival and prices of major commodities covering the period of ten years (2014-15 to 2023-24)

were collected from vitthal krushi utpanna bazar pvt. Ltd. in washim. The compound growth rate of arrival and prices of major commodities was worked out by using exponential form of equation as below

Compound growth rate

$$Y = ab^t$$

Where ,

Y= Monthly arrivals/prices

a = Constant

b = Trend Coefficient

t = Time period

Annual compound growth rate in percentage was calculated by

$$CGR\% = [Antilog (b-1)*100]$$

Variability in arrival and prices

$$\text{Coefficient variation} = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100$$

Where,

 σ = Standard deviation

X = Variable

 μ = Arithmetic mean

N = Number of observation

Correlation between arrival and prices

$$r_{xy} = \frac{Cov x,y}{\sigma x \sigma y}$$

Where,

r = Correlation coefficient

x = Arrival mean

y = Prices mean

Cov(x ,y) = Co variance between x and y

 σ_x = Standard deviation of x σ_y = Standard deviation of y

Seasonal indices in arrival and prices

$$\text{Seasonal Indices} = \frac{\text{Monthly arrivals/prices}}{\text{Average of arrivals/prices}} \times 100$$

Statistical Tool (Henry Garrett's ranking technique)

$$\text{Percent position} = 100(R_{ij} - 0.5)/N_j$$

Where,

 R_{ij} = Rank given for i^{th} problem by j^{th} individual N_j = Number of problems ranked by j^{th} individual.

Result and Discussion**Table 1: Profile of Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim, District.**

Sr.no.	Particulars	Activities
1.	Name of the market committee	Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim
2.	Date of Incorporation	2 July 2012
3.	Company Status	Active
4.	Authority Administering the Act	Director of Marketing Maharashtra State, Pune
5.	Class of Company	Private
6.	Authorized Capital	Rs.100,000
7.	Paid up Capital	Rs. 100,000
8.	Number of Employees	45
9.	Method of Sale	By Open Auction From 900a.m. onwards
10.	Number of Employees	45
11.	Company Whether listed or Not	Unlisted
12.	Extend of Market Area	35 villages of Washim
13.	Market Intelligence Method used for	- News Papers. - Notice Board
14.	Amenities	- Auction Platform - Auction hall - Canteen - Godowns

Table 2 : Compound growth rate in arrival and prices of Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim .

Sr.no.	Crops	Arrivals	Prices
		CGR(%)	CGR (%)
1.	Soyabean	-0.44***	0.59***
2.	Pigeon pea	-6.74***	0.29***
3.	Gram	0.13***	-0.09***
4.	Turmeric	2.19***	0.16**

(***, ** indicates significance at 1 and 5 per cent level of significance)

The table 2 shows the compound growth rate (CGR) of arrivals and prices for various crops at Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim. Soyabean arrivals have decreased (-0.44%) while prices increased (0.59%), both significant at 1%. Pigeon pea has a sharp

decline in arrivals (-6.74%) with a slight price rise (0.29%), also significant at 1%. Gram arrivals slightly increased (0.13%) but prices fell (-0.09%), both significant at 1%. Turmeric arrivals grew (2.19%), while prices showed a modest rise (0.16%), significant at 5%.

Table 3 : Coefficient of Variability (CV) in the arrival of soyabean commodities:

Years	Arrival		Prices	
	Mean (qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (qtl)	CV(%)
2014	48942.3	43.41	4097.4	18.85
2015	36145.3	118.8	3222.5	15.74
2016	43108.6	67.82	3317.1	13.88
2017	63206.2	50.46	2762.4	4.73
2018	81265	37.5	3448.3	5.58
2019	103008	56	3643.9	3.81
2020	61192.8	99.79	3768.5	5.91
2021	42682.8	98.82	5418.5	38.13
2022	30825.6	56.19	5969.7	13.61
2023	28075.4	61.03	4913.2	3.78

From the above table shows 3 significant variability in soybean arrivals and prices from 2014 to 2023. Arrival variability (CV%) is highest in 2015 (118.8%) and 2020 (99.79%), indicating unstable supply, while

prices were more stable, with the highest price variability in 2021 (38.13%). Despite fluctuations in arrivals, prices remained relatively stable, with the lowest CV in 2019 (3.81%) and 2023(3.78%).

Table 4: Coefficient of Variability (CV) in the arrivals and prices of Pigeon pea commodities:

Years	Arrival		Prices	
	Mean (qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (qtl)	CV (%)
2014	15316.5	161.4	5534.5	25.36
2015	15292.0	169.8	6469.2	29.74
2016	6202.25	53.95	7282.1	20.05
2017	11025.3	85.61	3938.0	7.28
2018	7115.17	88.71	3639.8	32.58
2019	5644.33	75.35	5301.6	4.63
2020	10396.2	123.1	5140.5	35.13
2021	7622.42	44.89	6040.3	5.98

2022	4819	49.91	6411.2	9.62
2023	3586.5	84.42	9654.3	19.27

The table 4 shows high variability in pigeon pea arrivals, with the highest in 2015 (CV 169.8%) and the lowest in 2021 (CV 44.89%).

Price variability is more stable, with the highest in 2020 (CV 35.13%)

and the lowest in 2019 (CV 4.63%), indicating more price stability compared to arrivals.

Table 5: Coefficient of Variability (CV) in the arrivals and prices of Gram commodities:

Year	Arrival		Prices	
	Mean (qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (qtl)	CV (%)
2014	4443.3	84.53	4518.5	22.12
2015	5396.5	74.33	4642.6	21.08
2016	3706.4	102.5	6559.1	29.95
2017	7456.6	51.37	5230.8	20.24
2018	11965.8	58.5	3665.2	11.06
2019	11330.8	56.52	4206.7	3.51
2020	6673	79.59	3822.1	34.13
2021	6646.8	74.73	4457.9	6.23
2022	6589.4	93.96	4238.5	4.64
2023	5603.5	129.4	3659.1	62.23

The table 5 shows considerable variability in gram arrivals, with the highest in 2023 (CV 129.4%) and the lowest in 2017 (CV 51.37%).

Price variability is relatively stable, with the highest in 2023 (CV

62.23%) and the lowest in 2019 (CV 3.51%), indicating greater fluctuations in arrivals compared to prices.

Table 6 : Coefficient of Variability (CV) in the arrivals and prices of Turmeric commodities:

Year	Arrival		Prices	
	Mean (qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (qtl)	CV (%)
2014	1726.5	165.5	5774.5	23.02
2015	2221.2	163.29	5553	42.14
2016	912.25	91.34	6688.1	18.9
2017	1552	155.8	5715.5	35.37
2018	824.33	124.7	4872.4	61.03
2019	25845	108.8	5259.5	9.78
2020	3903.5	103.3	3936.2	47.1
2021	5078.2	82.89	5199.1	48.41
2022	6685	87.89	6253	12.51
2023	7144.5	139.8	8821	38.89

The table 6 shows high variability in turmeric arrivals, with the highest in 2014 (CV 165.5%) and the lowest in 2021 (CV 82.89%).

Price variability is more stable, with the highest in 2018 (CV 61.03%) and

the lowest in 2019 (CV 9.78%), indicating significant fluctuations in both arrivals and prices over the years.

Table 7 : Correlation between arrivals and prices of major agricultural commodities.

(2014-15 to 2023-2024)

Sr.no.	Commodity	Correlation coefficient
1.	Soyabean	-0.49
2.	Pigeon pea	-0.37
3.	Gram	-0.50*
4.	Turmeric	0.44*

The above table 7 shows the correlation between arrivals and prices of major agricultural commodities from 2014-15 to 2023-24. Soyabean (-0.49) and pigeon pea (-0.37) have moderate negative correlations, meaning as arrivals increase, prices tend to decrease. Gram shows a

significant negative correlation (-0.50*), while turmeric has a significant positive correlation (0.44*), indicating that as turmeric arrivals increase, prices also tend to rise.

Table 8: Seasonal indices of arrival and prices Selected commodities in Vitthal Krushi Utpanna Bazar pvt. Ltd. Washim .

Months	Soyabean		Pigeon pea		Gram		Turmeric	
	Arrival	Prices	Arrival	Prices	Arrival	Prices	Arrival	Prices
Jan	123.66	95.84	111.5	90.84	34.72	99.92	45.69	100.0
Feb	106.11	103.8	157.2	93.16	118.9	93.61	24.07	76.72
March	92.76	99.27	237.2	96.63	240.1	91.66	21.69	64.16
April	79.33	110.2	189.8	99.11	180.0	100.7	213.0	110.0
May	70.88	112.8	194.0	101.3	145.9	103.8	315.8	102.3
June	68.44	106.3	91.74	112.2	111.9	98.63	152.4	109.2

July	60.30	106.6	78.02	99.53	76.32	103.2	138.1	108.8
August	57.68	87.69	36.49	102.4	50.55	92.26	96.18	125.7
Sept	51.27	96.82	32.16	110.7	71.15	101.1	85.35	104.4
Oct	118.26	87.49	25.74	102.7	68.48	103.3	42.46	101.3
Nov	185.83	95.14	22.69	99.59	53.41	110.6	29.20	98.63
Dec	185.46	97.84	23.33	91.71	48.44	100.8	35.79	98.39

The table 8 state that the seasonal indices show fluctuations in both arrivals and prices of crops across the year in Vitthal Krushi Utppana Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim. Soybean arrivals peak in November (185.83) and December (185.46) with lower prices, while prices are higher in May (112.8). Pigeon pea arrivals are highest in March (237.2),

with prices peaking in September (110.7). Gram arrivals are also highest in March (240.1), while prices peak in November (110.6). Turmeric shows the highest arrivals in May (315.8) and April (213.0), with prices peaking in August (125.7). This indicates significant seasonality in both arrivals and prices across all crops.

Table 9 : Advantages of Selected farmer in Vitthal Krushi Utppana Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim.

Sr.no	Advantages	Total score	Average score	Rank
1.	Timely Payment	1496	63.2	I
2.	Anytime selling of product	1501	50.4	II
3.	Minimum losses of the commodity	1496	49.9	III
4.	Grading facilities available	1422	47.4	V
5.	Protected warehousing facilities	1377	45.9	VI
6.	Less waiting period while selling	1314	43.8	VII
7.	Remunerative prices for the commodity	1485	49.5	IV

From the above table 9 state that the Advantages of Selected farmer in Vitthal Krushi Utppana Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim. It shows that the first ranked in Timely payment of a farmer followed by anytime selling

of product, minimum losses of the commodity, grading facilities available, protected warehousing facilities, less waiting period while selling and Remunerative price for the commodity

Table 10 : Constraints faced by Selected farmers in Vitthal Krushi Utppana Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim.,

Sr.no	Constraints	Total Score	Average Score	Rank
1.	Less of Hamal	1471	49.03	I
2.	High Transportation charges	1551	51.97	II
3.	Non availability of accommodation	1529	50.70	III
4.	Technical Knowledge	1449	48.30	IV

The table 10 show the selected farmers in Vitthal Krushi Utppana Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim Ranked first is the less of labour (Hamal), indicating that the shortage of workers is a major challenge. High transportation charges are ranked second, highlighting the cost burden associated with moving goods. The third-ranked issue is the non-availability of accommodation, suggesting a need for better living or storage facilities. Lastly, the technical knowledge notable constraint, Addressing these issues can significantly improve farmers' operational efficiency and income.

Conclusion

The Vitthal Krushi Utppana Bazar Pvt. Ltd. in Washim the market provides essential infrastructural facilities that facilitate smooth transactions for farmers.

It is revealed from the results that ,the compound growth rates indicate a general decline in arrivals for most crops, turmeric stands out with a positive growth trajectory.

The variability analysis highlights significant fluctuations in both arrivals and prices, suggesting that factors such as production variability and market demand significantly impact these commodities. The negative correlations between arrivals and prices for soybean, pigeon pea, and gram reinforce the inverse relationship observed, where increased arrivals tend to drive down prices.

Seasonal indices indicate distinct periods of peak arrivals and prices, which farmers can leverage for better decision-making.

It is concluded that, Farmers perceive various advantages in the market, particularly in terms of timely payments and opportunities for selling

their products, which contribute to smoother market transactions and reduced exploitation. However, significant constraints, such as a lack of Hamal and high transportation costs, pose challenges to farmers' profitability and market access.

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